

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TUNGSTEN(VI) CHLORIDE. PART I

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The amino derivatives of tungsten(VI) chloride have been prepared by the action of tungsten(VI) chloride on some mono- and di-amines, their properties studied and structures discussed.

Spacu (*Bull. Sect. Sci. Acad. Roumaine*, 1940, 22, 329) studied WCl_6 -ammonia system tensimetrically at -75° ; he removed associated ammonia at various temperatures up to 0° and observed the formation of $WCl_6 \cdot 6NH_3$. Fowles and Osborne (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2275) prepared $WCl_6 \cdot 4NH_3$ and $WCl_6 \cdot 6NH_3$ by passing dry ammonia gas through a solution of WCl_6 in CCl_4 , and observed the formation of various ammono basic tungsten(VI) chlorides by subsequent ammonolysis of the compounds.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of compounds by treating tungsten(VI) chloride with aromatic primary mono- and di-amines in CCl_4 .

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines used were of Merck's or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. Carbon tetrachloride ("Analar") was dried over and distilled from P_2O_5 immediately before use.

Tungsten(VI) chloride was prepared by the action of chlorine on pure tungsten powder (Messrs. Johnson and Matthey) at 600° in a quartz tube in the complete absence of oxygen. Traces of tungsten(VI) oxychlorides were also formed but were sublimed off. Excess of chlorine was removed by passing dry deoxidised nitrogen. A solution of tungsten(VI) chloride, dissolved in CCl_4 , was used in all the experiments.

Procedure.—A dilute solution of the amine in dry CCl_4 was slowly added to tungsten(VI) chloride solution with constant shaking till complete precipitation, leaving the amine in slight excess. The product was transferred to a sintered glass funnel and washed with dry CCl_4 till free of amine, all these operations having been carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere. Finally the product was dried in vacuum.

A weighed quantity of the compound was digested with HNO_3 (conc.) for several hours on a water bath. It was then evaporated to dryness, ignited, and weighed as WO_3 .

Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method as $AgCl$, and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method.

The compounds of tungsten(VI) chloride with mono- and diamines prepared are listed in Tables I and II.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in CCl_4 , ether, benzene, and acetone but sparingly soluble in ethanol; these are fairly stable in dry atmosphere but, when exposed to moist air, absorb moisture and decompose. When heated, these compounds decompose before melting. The aqueous extract of the compounds responds to the test for chlorine showing thereby that chlorine is in an ionisable state. The compounds formed with diamines are

are comparatively stable with respect to those with monoamines, due probably to chelation. These are decomposed by acids and alkalis. On heating with soda lime, the corresponding amines separate out and condense on the cooler parts of the test tube. All the compounds respond to the diazo test.

TABLE I
With primary monoamines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Aniline	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Grey	19.45	19.27	22.30	22.28	8.73	8.80
2. α -Naphthylamine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Bluish grey	14.72	14.66	16.88	16.95	6.65	6.69
3. β - ..	..	Do	14.60	..	16.96	..	6.65	..
4. o -Toluidine	$[\text{W}(\text{CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Light ash	17.64	17.71	20.50	20.48	8.03	8.09
5. m - ..	..	Do	17.80	..	20.42	..	8.05	..
6. p - ..	..	Light brown	17.72	..	20.36	..	8.07	..
7. o -Anisidine	$[\text{W}(\text{CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Bluish grey	16.40	16.21	18.53	18.75	7.41	7.40
8. m - ..	..	Blue	16.12	..	18.70	..	7.37	..
9. p - ..	..	Bluish grey	16.34	..	18.55	..	7.39	..
10. o -Phenetidine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Dirty grey	15.10	15.09	17.56	17.45	6.88	6.90
11. m - ..	..	Light brown	15.26	..	17.40	..	6.89	..
12. p - ..	..	Light grey	15.18	..	17.46	..	6.87	..
13. Benzylamine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Pale yellow	17.62	17.71	20.53	20.48	8.08	8.10

TABLE II
With diamines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Benzidine	$[\text{W}(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Grey	19.58	19.39	22.32	22.42	8.83	8.855
2. o -Toluidine	$[\text{W}(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_3)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Bluish grey	17.77	17.81	20.54	20.60	8.12	8.135
3. o -Phenylenediamine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Reddish brown	25.28	25.52	29.64	29.52	11.62	11.66
4. m - ..	..	Greenish grey	25.46	..	29.56	..	11.64	..
5. p - ..	..	Light grey	25.60	..	29.50	..	11.64	..
6. Dimethyl- p -phenylenediamine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NHCH}_3)_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Dark brown	22.64	22.85	26.70	26.44	10.43	10.44
7. m -Toluylenediamine	$[\text{W}(\text{CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NH}_2)_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Light blue	24.20	24.12	27.90	27.89	10.99	11.01
8. Dianisidine	$[\text{W}(\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{NH}_2)\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)\text{OCH}_3)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Dirty pink	16.48	16.29	18.62	18.85	7.42	7.44
9. Phenylhydrazine	$[\text{W}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH.NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_6$	Buff	25.38	25.52	29.62	29.52	11.62	11.65

DISCUSSION

The effective atomic number of tungsten in these compounds is 80, which is not a stable configuration, and therefore the compounds, though stable in the dry atmosphere at the room temperature, begin to hydrolyse slowly on exposure to moist air, or when treated with water, dilute NaOH or dilute Na_2CO_3 solution.

In all the cases studied, six molecules of a monoamine or three molecules of a diamine attach themselves to one molecule of tungsten(VI) chloride. It appears that the amines attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines, and may be represented as $[\text{W}(6\text{A})]\text{Cl}_6$, where A is a primary monoamine, and $[\text{W}(3\text{D})]\text{Cl}_6$, where D is a diamine.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities.

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Received May 24, 1960.